

DIHYDROTRIAZINES AS POTENTIAL ANTIMALARIALS

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Several dihydrotriazines have been prepared from arylamines, possessing either antibacterial or antimalarial activity.

The isolation of a dihydrotriazine as an active metabolite of Paludrine and the search for anticancer compounds led to the synthesis of this new class of compounds with antivitamin and antimalarial activity (Carrington *et al.*, *Nature*, 1951, 168, 1080; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1017; Crowther and Levi, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1953, 8, 93; Modest *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 855).

It was thought to be of interest to synthesise some triazines from arylamines possessing either antibacterial or antimalarial activity and to study their pharmacological characteristics. The arylamines used in these syntheses are *p*:*p'*-diaminodiphenyl sulphone and *p*-aminophenylmethyl sulphone, which possess antibacterial activity, and 4-hydroxy-3-diethylaminomethyl-aniline which has some antimalarial action. These arylamines were condensed with dicyandiamide and acetone in presence of hydrochloric acid to afford the corresponding dihydrotriazines as hydrochlorides.

In view of the marked antimalarial activity of 1-*p*-sulphonamidophenyl 2:4-diamino-1:6-dihydro-6:6-dimethyl-1:3:5-triazine hydrochloride (Ray *et al.*, *J. Indian Med. Assoc.*, 1954, 24, 169), an analogous compound (IV) was synthesised from sulphanilamide, dicyandiamide and methylethyl ketone.

Bami (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14C, 231) had attempted to synthesise the above compound (IV), but obtained *p*-sulphonamidophenylbiguanide hydrochloride (V) by the reaction of sulphanilamide, dicyandiamide and aqueous methylethyl ketone. Excess of hydrochloric acid in the above reaction led to the formation of *N*-*p*-sulphonamidophenyl-*N'*-guanylurea (VI).

The triazine compound (IV) was prepared in this laboratory by carrying out the reaction with a slight excess of hydrochloric acid and isolated as the hydrochloride. The ultraviolet absorption maximum of this compound in 0.01*N*-HCl was obtained at 244 $m\mu$ which was in the region characteristic for triazines of this type (Carrington *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1954). The absorption maximum of *N*-*p*-sulphonamidophenyl-*N'*-guanylurea (m.p. 236-38°), prepared by the method of Kundu and Ray (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 811), in 0.01*N*-HCl was 255-56 $m\mu$, whereas the absorption maximum of *p*-sulphonamidophenylbiguanide hydrochloride (Basu *et al.*, *Science & Culture*, 1952, 18, 45) in 0.01*N*-HCl was 266-67 $m\mu$. From the above observations it may be concluded that the compound in question can be definitely taken as a triazine derivative.

Syntheses of a similar type of triazine compounds from sulpha drugs are in progress.

None of the above triazine compounds have shown any significant antimalarial activity when tested against experimental malaria (N.K. Ray, *private communication*).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

p:*p'*-Di-(2:4-diamino-1:6-dihydro-6:6-dimethyl-1:3:5-triazine-1-yl)-diphenyl Sulphone Dihydrochloride (I).—*p*:*p'*-Diaminodiphenyl sulphone (1 g.), dicyandiamide (1 g.), acetone (150 c.c.), water (5 c.c.), and HCl (3 c.c.) were kept at room temperature (*ca.* 30°) for 24 hours. The solid separating from the clear solution was collected, washed with acetone, dried and crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 266–68°. (Found: N, 24.35. C₂₂H₂₈O₂N₁₀S.2HCl requires N, 24.69%). Ultraviolet absorption in 0.01N-HCl: λ_{max} 240 mμ. No free amino group was present as evidenced by the diazo test for aromatic amines.

2:4-Diamino-1-*p*-methylsulphonylphenyl-1:6-dihydro-6:6-dimethyl-1:3:5-triazine Hydrochloride (II).—A mixture of *p*-methylsulphonylaniline (5.6 g.), dicyandiamide (2.7 g.), acetone (150 c.c.), HCl (5 c.c.) and water (20 c.c.) was refluxed for 4 hours and left overnight at room temperature. The white crystals were collected and crystallised from aqueous alcohol, m.p. 242°. (Found: N, 20.88. C₁₂H₁₇O₂N₅S.HCl requires N, 21.12%). Ultraviolet absorption in 0.01N-HCl: λ_{max} 240 mμ.

2:4-Diamino-1-(4'-hydroxy-3'-diethylaminomethyl)-phenyl-1:6-dihydro-6:6-dimethyl-1:3:5-triazine Dihydrochloride (III).—3-Diethylaminomethyl-4-hydroxyacetanilide (Burckhalter *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1363) (10 g.) was refluxed for 1 hour with HCl (10 c.c.) and water (10 c.c.). The solution was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.)

and treated with acetone (400 c.c.) and water (50 c.c.) when a clear solution was formed. Dicyandiamide (2.5 g.) was added to the above solution and refluxed on a water-bath for 16 hours. The solvent was distilled off in vacuo. The viscous residue was triturated with acetone when a pinkish white solid₄ was obtained. This was collected and crystallised from acetone-alcohol mixture, m. p. 196°. (Found: N, 21.2. $C_{16}H_{26}ON_6 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 21.50%). Ultraviolet absorption in 0.01N-HCl: λ_{max} 234-36 and 276 m μ .

2:4-Diamino-1-p-sulphonamidophenyl-1:6-dihydro-6-methyl-6-ethyl-1:3:5-triazine Hydrochloride (IV).—A mixture of sulphanilamide (2.8 g.), methylethyl ketone (24 c.c.), water (2 c.c.), HCl (1.7 c.c.) and dicyandiamide (1.35 g.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 hours and left at room temperature overnight. The crystals were filtered and crystallised from aqueous alcohol, m.p. 210°. (Found: N, 22.22. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2N_6S \cdot HCl, H_2O$ requires N, 23.04%). Ultraviolet absorption in 0.01N-HCl: λ_{max} 244 m μ .

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